

HIV in Brazil: Analyzing Public Policies, Medication Access, and Epidemiology through a Compartmental Model

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Abstract— This study aimed to analyze the public policies for HIV control in Brazil, with a focus on prophylaxis and access to medication. At the time, the country was grappling with the presence of around 900,000 HIV-positive individuals, which propelled the continuous creation of governmental strategies to contain the disease's spread. Given this situation, the present work delved into the policies regarding prophylaxis and the acquisition of antiretroviral drugs, seeking to deepen the understanding of the domestic market's functioning. A preliminary analysis revealed that, despite partnerships with private laboratories, the Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz) was not able to meet the national demand for medication back then, necessitating the procurement of drugs from private companies. Additionally, a correlation was identified between the Human Development Index (HDI) of Brazilian cities and access to prophylaxis, underscoring the importance of leveling populations to achieve more precise analyses. The study also introduced a theoretical compartmental epidemiological model at that time, with the purpose of comprehending variations in populations affected by HIV. Over time, it was envisaged that the parameters of this model could be adjusted for a more realistic simulation. At that point, the model presented in this work was predominantly theoretical, as some of the proposed compartments were based on assumptions. This research contributed to a deeper understanding of HIV control policies and their implications at that time, while also seeking to advance the understanding of epidemic dynamics through an innovative model.

Keywords — HIV, Public Policies, Access to Medication, Epidemiology, Compartmental Model

I. Introduction

The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), belonging to the *Lentivirus* genus within the *Retroviridae* family, is distinguished by its prolonged incubation period. Originating from Central-West African monkeys, HIV can lead to the development of Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS) in advanced stages of infection, debilitating the immune system and rendering the body susceptible to opportunistic infections [1, 2]. Transmission occurs via bodily fluids such as blood and its derivatives (plasma and serum), genital secretions, and transplanted organs. Less commonly, transmission has been reported through saliva and bites, with another established route being the sharing of sharp objects such as needles [1]. Health

professionals concur that individuals with undetectable viral loads do not sexually transmit the virus, providing encouraging prospects for reducing viral transmission [3]. Vertical transmission can occur from mother to child during pregnancy and childbirth; recent studies indicate approximately 70% efficacy in reducing transmission through the administration of antiretroviral therapy (ARV) to pregnant women and newborns [4]. When ARV therapy is administered pre-conception and viral load remains undetectable throughout pregnancy, transmission becomes virtually negligible.

The origins of the AIDS pandemic trace back to the 1920s, initially on a smaller scale and associated with the consumption of monkeys, also known as “Bushmeat.” The infection spread across Africa, reached Haiti, and subsequently extended to the United States and Europe. Upon infiltrating major urban centers, the disease disseminated globally, with estimates indicating that over 80 million individuals have fallen victim to the virus.

In Latin America, more than 2 million people coexist with HIV [2]. Advances in medication have enabled HIV-positive individuals to live without developing AIDS, primarily through the application of drug cocktails that combine various antiretroviral substances, capable of reducing the viral load to undetectable levels. Furthermore, specific combinations can and should be employed as prophylactic measures for pre- and post-exposure to the virus.

In Brazil, antiretroviral therapy has been accessible through the public health system (SUS) since 1996 [3]. This milestone has engendered a significant reduction in overall mortality rates and an increase in the survival of HIV-positive individuals, underscoring the positive impact of universal access to antiretroviral drugs [5]. Despite numerous attempts by pharmaceutical companies since 1983, the pursuit of an HIV vaccine has remained elusive due to the virus's high mutation rate during replication [1, 2]. While these vaccine research endeavors have yet to succeed, they have significantly contributed to advancing understanding of replication mechanisms. Nonetheless, even with these advancements, the availability of an HIV vaccine in the coming years remains uncertain.

The objective of this work is to comprehend the HIV epidemic on national territory, enabling the development of tools to combat the disease. To achieve this, the following three stages will be undertaken: (i) Extensive literature review

to concisely represent the origin of HIV and the dynamics of its propagation; (ii) Statistical and qualitative analysis of socio-economic indicators alongside HIV incidence, aiming to understand the correlation between the number of new cases and the variation in these indicators; and (iii) Proposal of a theoretical epidemiological model that represents the dynamics of infections in a population.

The impetus behind this undergraduate work lies in providing support for populations affected by the AIDS epidemic. Throughout the study, vital information about AIDS will be conveyed alongside tangible actions to address this global challenge. The intention is to stimulate positive change, extend assistance to affected populations, and foster a future characterized by enhanced health and well-being for all.

II. Education and Awareness: Pillars in Combating HIV in Brazil

Recent studies conducted in Brazil underscore the significance of education in HIV prevention. In a questionnaire administered to young individuals aged 19 to 26, 86% identified the Ministry of Health and its policies as the primary force for prevention, while 73.3% recognized schools as the main source of information on the subject. Conversely, merely 11.6% identified family as a substantial information source about HIV [6].

The initial cases in Brazil were detected shortly after the identification in the USA, and the Brazilian response was nearly immediate [7]. Presently, it is estimated that around 900 thousand individuals are HIV-positive in Brazil, with 35 thousand new cases and 11 thousand deaths reported in 2021. Despite these figures, the epidemic is considered stable.

The Brazilian HIV combat program is globally recognized for its efficiency in achieving the UNAIDS-established 90-90-90 targets [3]. These targets entail identifying 90% of cases, treating 90% of identified cases, and reducing viral load to undetectable levels in 90% of treated patients.

In Brazil, 84% of cases are detected. Of these, 75% undergo treatment, and 92% of treated patients achieve undetectable viral load [7]. Pioneering efforts were demonstrated by Brazil in the fight against HIV when, in 1996, contrary to World Bank recommendations, the country decided to universally and freely provide antiretroviral therapy to all HIV-positive individuals. More recently, also displaying pioneering actions, Brazil commenced the free provision of pre- and post-exposure prophylaxis therapies in 2018.

III. Data Analysis and Correlation of Indicators with HIV Incidence

For the data analysis, five distinct public databases were utilized. These databases encompassed the epidemiological panel per city, obtained through the official Brazilian epidemiological panel [8], from which case numbers were extracted; the Human Development Index (HDI) listing per municipality from Atlas Brazil [9]; results of the Basic

Education Development Index (IDEB) per municipality, as released by INEP [10]; and information on population and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per Capita per municipality, provided by IBGE [11, 12].

Those databases, by default, follow a simple structure containing the following information: City Name, City IBGE Code (a unique code for each city, making it easier to combine data from different databases, even with typos on city names) and the respective indicator for that database. For working purposes, a customized database was built containing both City Name and City IBGE Code, the used indicators and the amount of new cases of HIV infection. For an initial moment, it was aggregated to the database other indicators, such as the partial HDI, linked to health, education, longevity and income, an level of education related IDEB, but those were not used in the analysis.

When examining the distribution of new cases by ethnicity (Table 4), it is not feasible to pinpoint a particular ethnicity more prone to infection, as the case distribution mirrors the ethnic diversity of the country

TABLE 4. Ethnic Distribution of New Disease Cases.

Ethnicity	Percentage of New Cases
White	34.5
Black	10.8
Yellow	0.9
Mixed Race	48.5
Indigenous	0.4
Unknown	4.9

The aforementioned indicators underwent analyses using four statistical tools. HDI, GDP per Capita, IDEB, and population were compared with HIV incidence using Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients. If a value approximates 1 or -1, indicating a strong positive or negative correlation, this hypothesis is tested through a two-tailed T-Student test with a 5% tolerance interval. Additionally, the proportion of case number variation in relation to indicators was calculated (R^2) [13]. The results are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

Clearly, only population demonstrates a positive correlation with an increase in case numbers. Furthermore, as an independent variable, its variation best explains the variance in case numbers, as demonstrated in Table 3.

TABLE 5. Qualitative Analysis of HIV Incidence Distribution in Different HDI Groups, Considering Population in Millions (M). The acronyms NM and AI, in the table below, refer to Number of Municipalities and Avg. Incidence, respectively.

HDI	NM	Population	AI
Very High	44	30.9	18.7
High	1,889	111.3	10.5
Medium	2,233	45.3	8.2
Low	1,367	22.7	6.6
Very Low	32	0.7	4.5

TABLE 1. Results Regarding Pearson Correlation Coefficient Calculation

Vs. Number of New Cases	HDI	Population	GDP per Capita	Average IDEB
Pearson Correlation Coefficient	0.141	0.928	0.050	0.047
p-Value	6.10E-26	0	1.71E-04	4.45E-04

TABLE 2. Results Regarding Spearman Correlation Coefficient Calculation

Vs. Number of New Cases	HDI	Population	GDP per Capita	Average IDEB
Spearman Correlation Coefficient	0.221	0.715	0.142	0.165
p-Value	9.62E-63	0	2.65E-26	2.32E-35

TABLE 6. Qualitative Analysis of HIV Incidence Distribution Among Different Ranges of Average IDEB Scores, Considering Population in Millions (M). The acronyms NM and AI, in the table below, refer to Number of Municipalities and Avg. Incidence, respectively.

IDEB Score	NM	Total Population	AI
< 2	661	8.6	6.9
2 to 4	1,964	47.7	9
4 to 6	2,880	153.3	8.9
6 to 8	59	1.2	7.6
> 8	1	1.3	0

The indicators were also subjected to qualitative analysis, each parametrized differently. Detailed results are presented in Tables 5, 6, and 7.

TABLE 7. Qualitative Analysis of HIV Incidence Distribution Among Different Ranges of GDP *per capita* (in thousand Reais - R\$), considering Population in Millions (M). The acronyms NM and AI, in the table below, refer to Number of Municipalities and Avg. Incidence, respectively.

GDP <i>per capita</i> (R\$ 1.000)	NM	Population	AI
< 10	939	17.0	6.3
10 to 20	1,818	42.6	7.6
20 to 30	1,103	46.4	9.4
30 to 40	680	28.5	9.8
40 to 50	433	33.5	11.4
50 to 100	488	38.5	11.1
> 100	104	4.3	10.5

Scrutinizing the outcomes of qualitative analyses, it is evident that cities with higher HDI exhibit a greater virus incidence. This phenomenon arises due to the concentration of population in more developed urban areas.

The same bias influences the other analyses. There is a slight reduction in incidences as the IDEB score increases; however, there is also a reduction in the total population. In the case of GDP *per Capita*, no clear pattern can be discerned regarding variation in incidence as income concentration increases.

TABLE 3. Results Regarding Coefficient of Determination (R^2) Calculation

Vs. Number of New Cases	HDI	Population	GDP per Capita	Average IDEB
R^2	0.022	0.861	0.003	0.002

IV. Development and Evaluation of an Epidemiological Model for HIV Transmission

For the conceptualization of an epidemiological model, we adopted a compartmental-based SIR model (Susceptible [S], Infected [I] and Recovered [R]), where compartments were defined based on theoretical insights obtained during the work's conceptualization phase.

Fig. 1. Proposed Theoretical Model.

The model adheres to the standard compartmental model equations, represented by the following (1). We utilized the ODE45 tool in MATLAB for the numerical integration of equations, employing the fourth and fifth-order Runge-Kutta method [14, 15].

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \mu * (S + Im + Ind + Det + NTrat) - (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 - \alpha_4) * S \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dIm}{dt} = \alpha_1 * S \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dInd}{dt} = \alpha_2 * S - \alpha_6 * Ind \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dDet}{dt} = \alpha_3 * S - \alpha_7 * Det \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dN_{trat}}{dt} = \alpha_4 * S - \alpha_8 * N_{trat} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = \alpha_7 * Det + \alpha_8 * N_{trat} \quad (6)$$

The simulation was initiated with an arbitrary initial population of 17 individuals, of which 10 were susceptible and 7 were infected, being 5 of them undetectable, 1 detectable and 1 not treating. We considered Brazil's population growth rate to be 1.26%, the natural immunization rate to HIV as 0.5% [16], and the infection rate as 17.8 per 100,000 inhabitants. The parameters to achieve the 90-90-90 Goal were set as 58% for undetectable, 5% for detectable, and 37% for untreated, and multiplying these parameters by the infection rate, we reach for α_2 , α_3 and α_4 , respectively, 0.00010324; 0.0000089 and 0.00006586. Additionally, we assumed arbitrary values for α_5 and α_6 , namely 7% and 12% (please note that these parameters are not publicly available in Brazil). Finally, we fixed $\alpha_7 = 93\%$ and $\alpha_8 = 100\%$.

The simulation results are depicted in Figure 2 and Table 8. It is evident that the model is mathematically functional. However, due to the absence of real-world parameters and historical data, determining the accuracy of this model precisely is unfeasible.

Fig. 2. Simulation results in MATLAB.

TABLE 8. Simulation results: final populations

Compartment	Population
Susceptible	12
Immune	1
Undetected	1
Detected	0
Untreated	0
Deceased	2

A. A Theoretical Model for HIV Treatment and Vaccination

Based on recent theoretical findings and speculations about innovative vaccines and treatments, a second purely

theoretical model is proposed. This new model, also based on the SIR framework, incorporates the potential of promising stem cell treatments in addressing HIV 3. Additionally, the model encompasses vaccination strategies and conventional antiretroviral treatments. Its equations are formulated as presented below.

Fig. 3. Proposed Model for the Future.

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \mu * (\sum compartments) - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2) * S \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dIm}{dt} = \alpha_1 * I + \alpha_3 * S \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \alpha_2 * S - \alpha_3 * I - \alpha_4 * I - \alpha_5 * I - \alpha_6 * I \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dCT}{dt} = \alpha_5 * I - \alpha_7 * CT - \alpha_8 * CT \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{dARV}{dt} = \alpha_6 * I + \alpha_{12} * CTF - \alpha_9 * ARV - \alpha_{10} * ARV \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{dN_{trat}}{dt} = \alpha_4 * I + \alpha_{13} * CTF + \alpha_{15} * Ind + \alpha_{16} * Det - \alpha_{14} * N_{trat} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{dCTE}{dt} = \alpha_7 * CT - \alpha_{11} * CTE \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{dCTF}{dt} = \alpha_8 * CT - \alpha_{12} * CTF - \alpha_{13} * CTF \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{dInd}{dt} = \alpha_{10} * ARV - \alpha_{15} * Ind \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{dDet}{dt} = \alpha_9 * ARV - \alpha_{16} * Det \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \alpha_{11} * CTE \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = \alpha_{14} * N_{trat} + \alpha_{17} * Det \quad (18)$$

V. Conclusions

Following the completion of the statistical tests, it becomes evident that only the population shows a positive correlation with disease incidence, and no significant correlations can be discerned based on IDEB, HDI, or GDP per Capita.

Population also emerges as the independent variable that best explains the variation in HIV incidence. In the qualitative analysis, it was not possible to identify any ethnical group more susceptible to the virus. While discernible patterns exist in the analyses involving HDI and IDEB, it is important to note that these patterns are influenced by population size within the groups.

Clear patterns of incidence variation based on accumulated GDP per Capita were not identified. As for the epidemiological model, it demonstrates mathematical functionality. However, the lack of historical data and real-world parameters for the general public makes it impossible at the moment to determine its precision with confidence, creating room for further research if the proper data becomes available.

References

- [1] G. A. C. Blood *et al.*, “Human immunodeficiency virus (hiv),” *Transfusion Medicine and Hemotherapy*, vol. 43, no. 3, p. 203, 2016.
- [2] F. Barin, “Hiv/aids as a model for emerging infectious disease: Origin, dating and circumstances of an emblematic epidemiological success,” *La Presse Médicale*, vol. 51, no. 3, p. 104128, 2022.
- [3] UNAIDS, “Unaids: esforços para obter vacina contra hiv devem continuar apesar de falhas.” Unaid: esforços para obter vacina contra HIV devem continuar apesar de falhas, 2023.
- [4] E. Bouza, J. R. Arribas, B. Alejos, J. I. Bernardino, M. Coiras, P. Coll, J. Del Romero, M. J. Fuster, M. Górgolas, A. Gutiérrez, *et al.*, “Past and future of hiv infection. a document based on expert opinion,” *Revista Española de Quimioterapia*, vol. 35, no. 2, p. 131, 2022.
- [5] A. C. Reis, E. M. d. Santos, and M. M. d. Cruz, “A mortalidade por aids no brasil: um estudo exploratório de sua evolução temporal,” *Epidemiologia e Serviços de Saúde*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 195–205, 2007.
- [6] C. A. S. Ferreira and O. J. A. Neto, “Educação sobre hiv/aids: Avaliando a efetividade das políticas públicas brasileiras,” *Revista Brasileira de Sexualidade Humana*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 77–88, 2018.
- [7] A. S. Benzaken, L. Kerr, A. Ferreira, R. Alencar, A. M. d. Brito, G. Ana, L. Tomas, L. Ramone, J. Alves, L. Joppert, *et al.*, “The cascade of care for an integrated comprehensive approach to hiv prevention, care and treatment in brazil,” *Journal of the International AIDS Society*, vol. 22, no. 6, p. e25259, 2019.
- [8] M. da Saúde, “Indicadores e dados básicos do hiv/aids nos municípios brasileiros.” Indicadores e Dados Básicos do HIV/AIDS nos Municípios Brasileiros, 2022.
- [9] AtlasBR, “Ranking.” Ranking, 2022.
- [10] INEP, “Resultados.” Instituto Nacional de Estudos e Pesquisas Educacionais Anísio Teixeira | Inep, 2022.
- [11] IBGE, “Produto interno bruto dos municípios.” Produto Interno Bruto dos Municípios, 2022.
- [12] IBGE, “Estimativas da população.” Estimativas da População, 2022.
- [13] H. G. Arango, *Bioestatística: teórica e computacional. 2a edição.* Guanabara Koogan, Rio de Janeiro, 2005.
- [14] C. Garcia, “Modelagem e simulação de processos industriais e de sistemas eletromecânicos, 2ª edição,” *Ed EDUSP*, 2005.
- [15] J. Enderle and J. Bronzino, *Introduction to biomedical engineering.* Academic press, 2012.
- [16] A. Košmrli, E. L. Read, Y. Qi, T. M. Allen, M. Altfeld, S. G. Deeks, F. Pereyra, M. Carrington, B. D. Walker, and A. K. Chakraborty, “Effects of thymic selection of the t-cell repertoire on hla class i-associated control of hiv infection,” *Nature*, vol. 465, no. 7296, pp. 350–354, 2010.